

An Annotated Checklist of Indian Psephenidae (Coleoptera)

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Abstract

This catalog documents 28 valid species of the family Psephenidae from India, representing 9.3% of their global diversity. These species are divided into four subfamilies: Eubriinae (19 species, 5 genera), Eubrianacinae (2 species, 1 genus), Psepheninae (1 species, 1 genus), and Psephenoidinae (6 species, 3 genera). The valid name of the species as well as synonyms, and type localities are provided along with their distribution in India and the world. Interestingly, about two–thirds (21 species) of these Indian Psephenidae are found in the Himalayas, while 11 species occur in the north–east, two species each in the Deccan Peninsula and Western Ghats. Indian Psephenidae fauna remains understudied, highlighting the need for a nationwide, systematic survey to comprehensively document its diversity.

Key words: Biogeographic Zones of India, diversity, distribution, research gaps, taxonomy.

Introduction

Psephenidae beetles are found worldwide (except Antarctica) in moderately fast–flowing freshwater habitats such as streams, and rivers (Lee & Jäch, 1995; Short, 2017). They are characterized by the unique, penny–like, round and flat body shape of the larvae. Pupae and adults are generally terrestrial, although the pupae of the family Psephenoidinae are reportedly aquatic. Eggs are laid underwater. The larvae live in water and feed on algae that grow on submerged rocks and wood (Lee et al., 2016). This family encompasses five subfamilies (Afroeubriinae, Eubrianacinae, Eubriinae, Psepheninae, and Psephenoidinae), containing roughly 300 species in 5 subfamilies and 37 genera globally (Lee et al., 2007; Lee et al., 2016; Lee 2016a, 2016b). The Afroeubriinae subfamily, however, is restricted to the Ethiopian region (Lee et al., 2016). In the Palearctic region alone, there are over 100 species and two subspecies within 19 genera (Lee, 2016b). Despite this global diversity, a consolidated catalogue for Indian Psephenidae has yet to be published. To address this gap, this paper aims to provide distributional records of Indian Psephenidae, including an inventory of their occurrence by state and biogeographic zone. Additionally, the article highlights areas where further faunistic surveys and research are needed to comprehensively understand Psephenidae diversity within India.

Materials and methods

This catalogue draws upon the existing literature to provide a comprehensive record of Indian Psephenidae. For each species, the valid name as well as synonyms and type locations are listed. In addition, the catalogue contains important citations related to the taxonomic history of the species and its distribution in India (including details at state, district, and micro–site levels) as well as its global range. Genera and species are arranged alphabetically within their respective subfamilies. Classification, nomenclature, and global distribution are based on the work of Lee (2016b). Species with asterisks (*) have been reported exclusively from India.

We largely follow the approach of Rodgers et al. (2002), Chandra et al. (2018), and Singh et al. (2022), on the biogeographic classification of India, which divides India into the following ten biogeographic zones: Trans Himalaya, Himalaya, Desert, Semi-Arid, Gangetic Plains, Deccan Peninsula, Western Ghats, Northeast, Islands, and Coasts (Fig.1). The localities mentioned in the paper are classified according to their respective biogeographic zone in Table 1. None of the localities are found in the Trans-Himalaya, Desert, Semi-Arid, Gangetic Plains, Coastal, or Island zones. We adopt the Palaearctic regional boundaries outlined by Löbl & Löbl (2016) in their Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera to better understand distribution patterns of Indian species. The northern Indian states along the base of the Himalayas – Arunachal Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Himachal Pradesh, and Jammu & Kashmir – belong to the Palaearctic region. In contrast, the rest of India falls under the Oriental region.

Figure 1: Map of biogeographic zones of India showing number of species.

Table 1. Biogeographic zones applied to Psephenidae species recorded from India.

Biogeographic Zone	Localities mentioned in the paper
Himalaya	Jammu & Kashmir, Arunachal Pradesh (Dirang vicinity, Lower Dibang Valley, Hunli, Roing, Etalin, Jamiri–Sessa vicinity), Sikkim, West Bengal (Kalimpong, Darjeeling), Uttarakhand (Dehradun, Garhwal, Alomora, Kumaon: Haldwani, Ranikhet).
Western Ghats	Tamil Nadu (Annamalai Hills: Cinchona, Nilgiri Hills).
Deccan Peninsula	Madhya Pradesh (Jabalpur), Maharashtra (Lonvala), Tamil Nadu (Tiruchirappalli), Odisha (Similipal National Park).
North East	Manipur, Meghalaya (Khasi Hills: Cherrapunjee, Jaintia Hills, West Garo Hills: Nokrek National Park, Tura).

Results

Catalogue

Family **Psephenidae** Lacordaire, 1854

Subfamily **Eubrianacinae** Jakobson, 1913

Genus ***Odontanax*** Lee, Satô & Yang, 2000

Odontanax Lee, Satô & Yang, 2000: 151 (type species: *Eubrianax maculicollis* Fairmaire, 1888).

Odontanax laosensis (Pic, 1923)

Eubrianax laosensis Pic, 1923: 9.

Eubrianax tonkineus Pic, 1935: 16.

Odontanax laosensis: Lee et al., 2000: 160, figs., 25–28, 47; Lee et al., 2001: 360; Lee & Jäch, 2007: 237; Lee, 2016a: 155.

Type locality: Haut, Laos, Vientiane Vitalis.

Distribution in India: Arunachal Pradesh (Dirang vicinity) (Lee, 2016a) and Meghalaya (Jaintia Hills) (Lee et al., 2000).

Global Distribution: India, Laos (Lee et al., 2001), Nepal (Lee & Jäch, 2007), and Vietnam (Pic, 1923; Lee & Jäch, 2007).

Odontanax obscuripes (Pic 1914)*

Eubrianax obscuripes Pic 1914: 7.

Odontanax obscuripes: Lee et al., 2000: 166, figs., 42–45; Lee et al., 2001: 360.

Type locality: Tiruchirappalli “Trichonopoli”, Ind. Or.

Distribution in India: Tamil Nadu (Tiruchirappalli) (Lee et al., 2000) and Meghalaya (West Garo Hills: Nokrek National Park) (Lee et al., 2000).

Subfamily **Eubriinae** Lacordaire, 1857

Genus ***Dicranopselaphus*** Guérin–Méneville, 1861

Dicranopselaphus Guérin–Méneville, 1861: 531 (type species: *Dicranopselaphus lesuierii* Guérin–Méneville, 1861)

Alabameubria H. P. Brown, 1980: 188 (type species: *Alabameubria starki* H. P. Brown, 1980)

Furcipalpus Guérin–Méneville, 1861: 533 (type species: *Dicranopselaphus lesueurii* Guérin–Méneville, 1861)

Spineubria Nakane, 1952: 39 (type species: *Spineubria reticulata* Nakane, 1952)

Dicranopselaphus dentatus Lee, Yang & Satô, 2000*

Dicranopselaphus dentatus Lee, Yang & Satô, 2000: 563, figs. 14–17.

Type locality: Meghalaya, W Garo Hills, Balphakram NP “National Park”.

Distribution in India: Meghalaya (Garo Hills) (Lee et al., 2000).

Dicranopselaphus imparis Lee, Yang & Satô, 2000

Dicranopselaphus imparis Lee, Yang & Satô, 2000: 565, figs. 22–25; Lee & Jäch, 2007: 231; Lee, 2016a: 158; Lee, 2016b: 617.

Type locality: Tamdao, Pr. Vinhphu, Vietnam.

Distribution in India: Arunachal Pradesh (Lower Dibang Valley, Hunli) (Lee et al., 2000; Lee, 2016b).

Global Distribution: India, Laos, and Vietnam (Lee et al., 2000; Lee, 2016b).

Dicranopselaphus nepalensis Lee & Yang, 1996

Dicranopselaphus nepalensis Lee & Yang, 1996: 194, fig. 31; Lee et al., 2000: 566; Jäch et al., 2006: 450; Lee, 2016a: 158.

Type locality: E. Nepal, Basantapur.

Distribution in India: Arunachal Pradesh (Roing, Etalin) (Lee, 2016a), Sikkim (Lee et al., 2000), and West Bengal (Kalimpong, Darjeeling) (Lee et al., 2000).

Global distribution: India, Nepal (Lee & Yang, 1996).

Dicranopselaphus septemspinus Lee, Yang & Satô, 2000

Dicranopselaphus septemspinus Lee, Yang & Satô, 2000: 567, figs. 29–31; Lee, 2016a: 160.

Type locality: Myanmar “Burma”, N. Kachin, 10 miles S of Putao Mulashidi.

Distribution in India: Arunachal Pradesh (Jamiri–Sessa vicinity) (Lee, 2016a).

Global distribution: India, Myanmar (Lee et al., 2000).

Genus *Granuleubria* Jäch & Lee, 1994

Granuleubria Jäch & Lee, 1994: 225 (type species: *Drupeus atriceps* Pic, 1916).

Granuleubria atriceps (Pic, 1916)*

Drupeus atriceps Pic, 1916: 4.

Granuleubria atriceps: Jäch & Lee, 1994: 227, figs., 1–11, 21, 23; Lee & Yang, 1999: 266; Lee, 2016a: 161.

Type locality: India.

Distribution in India: Madhya Pradesh (Jabalpur) (Lee & Yang, 1999), Maharashtra (Lonvala) (Jäch & Lee, 1994) and Odisha (Similipal National Park) (Lee, 2016a).

Granuleubria marginata (Pic, 1944)*

Drupeus marginatus Pic 1944: 1.

Granuleubria marginata: Jäch & Lee, 1994: 229, fig. 26; Lee & Yang, 1999: 266, figs., 26–28; Jäch et al., 2006: 451; Lee, 2016b: 618.

Type locality: Dehra Dun, Dobhalwala.

Distribution in India: Uttarakhand (Dehradun) (Pic 1944; Jäch & Lee, 1994) and Tamil Nadu (Annamalai Hills: Cinchona) (Lee & Yang, 1999).

Granuleubria nigra Lee & Yang, 1999

Granuleubria nigra Lee & Yang, 1999: 270, figs., 33–35.

Type locality: India, Meghalaya, W Garo Hills, Nokrek NP.

Distribution in India: Meghalaya (Garo Hills: Nokrek National Park) (Lee & Yang, 1999).

Global Distribution: India, Nepal.

Genus *Macroebria* Pic, 1916

Macroebria Pic, 1916: 4 (type species: *Macroebria striatipennis* Pic, 1916)

Macroebria diffusa Lee, Yang & Satô, 1999

Macroebria diffusa Lee, Yang & Satô 1999: 183, fig. 1A–E; Jäch et al., 2006: 451; Lee, 2016a: 164; Lee, 2016b: 619.

Type locality: Vietnam, Lao Chau Prov., 12–15 km N. of Bin Lu.

Distribution in India: Arunachal Pradesh (Dirang Valley, Etalin) (Lee, 2016a), Meghalaya (Cherrapunjee) (Lee, 2016a), Sikkim (Lee et al., 1999), and West Bengal (Darjeeling, Kalimpong) (Lee et al., 1999).

Global Distribution: Bhutan (Lee, 2016b), China (Lee, 2016a; Lee et al., 1999), India, Laos (Lee, 2016a), Myanmar, Nepal (Lee et al., 1999), Thailand (Lee et al., 1999), and Vietnam (Lee et al., 1999).

Genus *Microebria* Lee & Yang, 1994

Microeubria Lee & Yang, 1994: 325 (type species: *Microeubria jaechi* Lee & Yang, 1994).

Microeubria minima (Champion, 1924)*

Eubria minima Champion, 1924: 250.

Microeubria minima: Lee & Jäch, 1996: 45, figs., 18–20; Lee & Yang, 1998: 370, fig. 1; Jäch et al., 2006: 451; Lee, 2016b: 619.

Type locality: Haldwani Div. Kumaon, India.

Distribution in India: Sikkim (Lee & Yang, 1998), Uttarakhand (Kumaon: Haldwani) (Champion, 1924; Lee & Jäch, 1996), and West Bengal (Darjeeling) (Lee, 2016b).

Microeubria reticula Lee & Jäch, 1996

Microeubria reticula Lee & Jäch, 1996: 49; Lee & Yang, 1998: 371; Jäch et al., 2006: 451; Lee, 2016b: 619.

Distribution in India: Sikkim (Lee & Yang, 1998) and West Bengal (Lee, 2016b).

Global distribution: India, Nepal (Lee, 2016b).

Microeubria semistriata (Champion, 1921)*

Eubria semistriata Champion, 1921: 204.

Microeubria semistriata: Lee & Jäch, 1996: 45, figs., 16–17; Lee & Yang, 1998: 370; Jäch et al., 2006: 451; Lee, 2016b: 619.

Type locality: S. Garhwal, Kumaon, 6500 ft., India.

Distribution in India: Sikkim (Lee, 2016b), Uttarakhand (Garhwal, Kumaon) (Champion, 1921; Lee & Jäch, 1996), and West Bengal (Darjeeling) (Lee, 2016b).

Microeubria wittmeri Lee & Yang, 1998*

Microeubria wittmeri Lee & Yang, 1998: 371, figs., 2–6; Jäch et al., 2006: 451; Lee, 2016b: 619.

Type locality: India, West Bengal, Labong, 1800/1900 m, distr. Darjeeling.

Distribution in India: West Bengal (Darjeeling) (Lee & Yang, 1998).

Genus *Schinostethus* Waterhouse 1880

Schinostethus Waterhouse 1880: 563 (type species: *Schinostethus nigricornis* Waterhouse, 1880)

Cophaesthetus Waterhouse, 1880: 566 (type species: *Cophaesthetus opacus* Waterhouse, 1880)

Drupeubria Nakane, 1952: 37 (type species *Drupeus brevis* Lewis, 1895)

Subgenus *Schinostethus* Waterhouse 1880

Schinostethus (Schinostethus) niger Lee, Yang & Brown, 1993

Schinostethus niger Lee, Yang & Brown, 1993: 687, figs., 6, 13, 24; Lee et al., 1998: 309; Jäch et al., 2006: 452; Lee, 2016b: 619.

Type locality: India, Manipur.

Distribution in India: Manipur (Lee et al., 1993), Sikkim (Lee et al., 1998), and West Bengal (Lee, 2016b).

Global Distribution: India, Nepal (Lee et al., 1998).

Schinostethus (Schinostethus) nigricornis Waterhouse, 1880

Schinostethus nigricornis Waterhouse, 1880: 564; Champion 1924: 251; Lee et al., 1993: 684, figs., 2, 10, 17, 21; Lee et al., 1998: 310; Jäch et al., 2006: 452; Hájek 2015: 689; Lee 2016a: 168; Lee, 2016b: 619.

Drupeus indicus Pic, 1916: 3.

Grammeubria diversipes Pic, 1923: 10.

Type locality: China.

Distribution in India: Jammu & Kashmir (Lee et al., 1998), Meghalaya (Tura, West–Garo Hills, Nokrek National Park) (Lee et al., 1998; Lee 2016a), Sikkim (Lee et al., 1998), Uttarakhand (Dehradun, Garhwal, Alomora, Kumaon) (Lee et al., 1993), and West Bengal (Darjeeling) (Lee et al., 1993, 1998).

Global Distribution: Bhutan (Lee et al., 1998), China (Hájek 2015; Lee et al., 1998), India, Laos (Lee 2016a; Lee et al., 1998), Malaysia (Lee et al., 1993; Lee 2016a), Myanmar (Lee et al., 1993), Nepal (Lee 2016a; Lee et al., 1998), Thailand (Lee et al., 1993, 1998; Lee 2016a), and Vietnam (Lee et al., 1998).

Subgenus *Sundodrupeus* Pic, 1916

Sundodrupeus Pic, 1916: 4 (type species: *Drupeus pruinosus* Pic, 1916)

Schinostethus (Sundodrupeus) brancuccii Lee, 2016a*

Schinostethus (Sundodrupeus) brancuccii Lee, 2016a: 170, fig. 5, 29–32.

Type locality: India, Meghalaya, South West of Cherrapunjee.

Distribution in India: Meghalaya (Cherrapunjee) (Lee, 2016a).

Schinostethus (Sundodrupeus) geiseri Lee, 2016a*

Schinostethus (Sundodrupeus) geiseri Lee, 2016a: 173, figs. 9, 37, 38, 39, 40.

Type locality: India, Arunachal Pradesh, 8km S Jamiri–Sessa vicinity.

Distribution in India: Arunachal Pradesh (Jamiri–Sessa) (Lee, 2016a).

Schinostethus (Sundodrupeus) dembickyi Lee, 2016a

Schinostethus (Sundodrupeus) dembickyi Lee, 2016a: 172, figs. 6, 33–36.

Type locality: India, Arunachal Pradesh. 8 km., S Jamiri–Sessa vicinity.

Distribution in India: Arunachal Pradesh (Jamiri–Sessa) (Lee, 2016a) and Meghalaya (Tura) (Lee, 2016a).

Global Distribution: India, Nepal (Lee, 2016a).

Schinostethus (Sundodrupeus) sipekorum Hájek, 2015*

Schinostethus (Sundodrupeus) sipekorum Hájek, 2015: 686, figs., 1–7.

Type locality: India, Meghalaya, East Khasi Hills, 11 km South West Cherrapunjee, Laitkynsew.

Distribution in India: Meghalaya (Khasi Hills: Cherrapunjee) (Hájek, 2015).

Schinostethus (Sundodrupeus) transversus Lee & Jäch, 2007*

Schinostethus (Sundodrupeus) transversus Lee & Jäch, 2007: 239, figs. 15–19.

Type locality: India, Uttarakhand (Uttaranchal) 30 km North Bageshwar West Loharket [village]).

Distribution in India: Uttarakhand (Lee & Jäch, 2007).

Subfamily **Psepheninae** Lacordaire, 1854

Genus *Mataeopsephus* Waterhouse, 1876

Mataeopsephus Waterhouse, 1876: 16 (type species: *Mataeopsephus nitidipennis* Waterhouse, 1876)

Betelmis Matsumura, 1915: 214 (type species: *Betelmis japonicus* Matsumura, 1915)

Sinopsephenus Nakane, 1964: 50 (type species: *Psephenus chinensis* Nakane, 1964)

Mataeopsephus tenuipes (Champion, 1921) *

Psephenus tenuipes Champion, 1921: 202.

Mataeopsephus tenuipes: Lee et al., 2003: 493; Jäch et al., 2006: 452; Lee 2016a: 620.

Type locality: Almora, Kumaon, Uttar Pradesh, North India.

Distribution in India: Uttarakhand (Almora, Kumaon) (Champion, 1921; Lee et al., 2003a).

Subfamily **Psephenoidinae** Bollow, 1938

Genus *Afropsephenoides* Basilewsky, 1959

Afropsephenoides Basilewsky, 1959: 30 (type species: *Afropsephenoides marlieri* Basilewsky, 1959).

Afropsephenoides volatilis (Champion, 1924)

Psephenoides volatilis Champion, 1924: 251.

Afropsephenoides volatilis: Jeng et al., 2006b: 107, figs., 1–7; Jäch et al., 2006: 452; Lee, 2016b: 620.

Type locality: Haldwani, Kumaon, Uttaranchal, north western India

Distribution in India: Uttarakhand (Haldwani, Kumaon) (Champion, 1924).

Global distribution: India, Nepal (Jeng et al., 2006b), and Pakistan (Jeng et al., 2006b).

Genus *Micrebrianax* Pic, 1922

Micrebrianax Pic, 1922: 5 (type species: *Eubrianax (Micrebrianax) flabellicornis* Pic, 1922)

Micrebrianax bellus Jeng & Jäch, 2006*

Micrebrianax bellus Jeng & Jäch, 2006 (in Jeng et al., 2006a): 70, figs., 3, 4–14, 5.

Type locality: North–East India: Meghalaya, West Garo Hills, Nokrek NP.

Distribution in India: Meghalaya (Garo Hills) (Jeng et al., 2006a).

Genus *Psephenoides* Gahan, 1914

Psephenoides Gahan, 1914: 189 (type species: *Psephenoides immsi* Gahan, 1914)

Psephenoides gahani Champion, 1920

Psephenoides gahani Champion, 1920: 194, figs., 1–2; Böving, 1926: 381–388, figs., 1–17; Jäch et al., 2006: 452; Lee, 2016b: 620.

Type locality: Uttarakhand (Ranikhet, Kumaon, 3000 ft.).

Distribution in India: Uttarakhand (Ranikhet, Dehradun: Lachiwala) (Champion, 1920) and Tamil Nadu (Nilgiri Hills) (Champion, 1920).

Global distribution: India, Nepal (Lee, 2016b).

Psephenoides immsi Gahan, 1914

Psephenoides immsi Gahan, 1914: 189, figs.; Jäch et al., 2006: 452; Lee, 2016b: 620.

Type locality: Uttarakhand, Bhowali, Kumaon, 5700 ft.

Distribution in India: Uttarakhand (Kumaon) (Gahan, 1914).

Global distribution: Bhutan (Lee, 2016b), India (Gahan, 1914) and Nepal (Lee, 2016b).

Psephenoides rajouri Chowdhari, 1977*

Psephenoides rajouri Chowdhari, 1977: 50; Jäch et al., 2006: 452; Bhagat, 2013: 93.

Type locality: Jammu & Kashmir, Rajouri.

Distribution in India: Jammu & Kashmir (Rajouri) (Chowdhari, 1977).

Psephenoides subopacus (Pic, 1954)

Micrebrianax subopacus Pic, 1954: 64.

Psephenoides subopacus: Jäch et al., 2006: 452; Lee et al., 2007: 505, fig. 1H, U, 3J, N, 8C; Lee, 2016b: 620.

Psephenoides wuhongi Yang, 1997: 231.

Distribution in India: Uttarakhand (Lee, 2016b).

Global distribution: China, India, Japan, Nepal and Taiwan (Jäch et al., 2006; Lee, 2016b).

Discussion

This catalog documents 28 species of aquatic beetles belonging to the Psephenidae family. This represents a significant 9.3% of their global diversity. These species are classified into four subfamilies: Eubriinae (most abundant with 19 species across 5 genera), Eubrianacinae (2 species in 1 genus), Psepheninae (1 species, 1 genus), and Psephenoidinae (6 species spread across 3 genera) (Fig. 2). Notably, 14 of these species (half of the recorded species) are found exclusively in India.

Figure 2: Graph showing number of subfamilies, genera and species in world and India.

Our data reveals an interesting biogeographic distribution for the Indian species. They are primarily found in two realms: the Palearctic (21 species) and the Oriental (15 species). This suggests absence of species reported from India in Nearctic, Afrotropic, Neotropic, Australasia, and Oceania. Interestingly, India contributes 22 species to the Palearctic region's total of 100 known Psephenidae species (Lee, 2016b). The distribution of genera within the family also shows distinct patterns. Table 2 compares the global and Indian number of species along with their distributional ranges in the genera, known from India.

Table 2. Number of species in Indian genera from the world and India. Distribution ranges of the genera broadly follow Lee et al. (2016).

Subfamily	Genus	Distribution Range	World	India
Eubrianacinae	<i>Odontanax</i> Lee, Satô & Yang, 2000	India, Nepal, Sri Lanka, South-east Asia.	12	2
Eubriinae	<i>Dicranopselaphus</i> Guérin-Méneville, 1861	Oriental and eastern, Palearctic Regions, North America, Mexico, Guatemala.	40	4
	<i>Granuleubria</i> Jäch & Lee, 1994	Turkey, Iran, Pakistan, Nepal, India, Thailand, Vietnam, Borneo.	8	3
	<i>Macroebria</i> Pic, 1916	Sri Lanka, Himalaya, China, Japan, Taiwan, South-east Asia.	21	1
	<i>Microebria</i> Lee & Yang, 1994	Himalaya, Southeast, Asia.	8	4
	<i>Schinostethus</i> Waterhouse 1880	Himalaya, China, Japan, Taiwan, South-east Asia.	25	7
Psepheninae	<i>Mataeopsephus</i> Waterhouse, 1876	India, China, Russian, Far East, Korea, Taiwan, Vietnam.	12	1
Psephenoidinae	<i>Afropsephenoides</i> Basilevsky, 1959	Ethiopian Region, Pakistan, Himalaya.	3	1
	<i>Micreubrianax</i> Pic, 1922	Himalaya, South-east Asia.	4	1
	<i>Psephenoides</i> Gahan, 1914	Himalaya, China, Taiwan, Japan, South-east Asia.	8	4

As noted by Brown (1981), most genera tend to be restricted to specific zoogeographic regions, with no truly cosmopolitan examples. Additionally, species diversity is higher in tropical zones compared to temperate regions, with the Oriental Region representing the highest number of species (Lee et al., 2016). With regards to Indian states, the highest diversity is found in Uttarakhand (10 species) and Meghalaya (10 species) followed by West Bengal (8 species), Arunachal Pradesh and Sikkim (7 species each), Tamil Nadu (3 species), and Jammu & Kashmir (2 species). Interestingly, the Himalayas harbour two-thirds (21 species) of India's Psephenidae, while the north-east has 11 species, the Deccan Peninsula and Western Ghats each has two (Fig. 1, Table 3). Notably, most Indian states lack records, and only Manipur, Maharashtra, Odisha, and Madhya Pradesh have a single reported species (Fig. 3). This uneven distribution suggests the need for further surveys to comprehensively understand the true diversity of Psephenidae across India.

Figure 3: Map of Indian state showing number of recorded species.

Table 3. Distribution of Psephenidae in biogeographic zones of India.

SN	Species Name	Trans Himalaya	Himalaya	Desert	Semi-Arid	Gangetic Plains	Deccan Peninsula	Western Ghats	Northeast	Islands	Coasts
1.	<i>Odontanax laosensis</i>		+						+		
2.	<i>Odontanax obscuripes</i>						+		+		
3.	<i>Dicranopselaphus dentatus</i>								+		
4.	<i>Dicranopselaphus imparis</i>		+								
5.	<i>Dicranopselaphus nepalensis</i>		+								
6.	<i>Dicranopselaphus septemspinus</i>		+								

7.	<i>Granuleubria atriceps</i>							+				
8.	<i>Granuleubria marginata</i>		+						+			
9.	<i>Granuleubria nigra</i>									+		
10.	<i>Macroebria diffusa</i>		+							+		
11.	<i>Microebria minima</i>		+									
12.	<i>Microebria reticula</i>		+									
13.	<i>Microebria semistriata</i>		+									
14.	<i>Microebria wittmeri</i>		+									
15.	<i>Schinostethus</i> (<i>Schinostethus</i>) <i>niger</i>		+							+		
16.	<i>Schinostethus</i> (<i>Schinostethus</i>) <i>nigricornis</i>		+							+		
17.	<i>Schinostethus</i> (<i>Sundodrupeus</i>) <i>brancuccii</i>									+		
18.	<i>Schinostethus</i> (<i>Sundodrupeus</i>) <i>geiseri</i>		+									
19.	<i>Schinostethus</i> (<i>Sundodrupeus</i>) <i>dembickyi</i>		+							+		
20.	<i>Schinostethus</i> (<i>Sundodrupeus</i>) <i>sipekorum</i>									+		
21.	<i>Schinostethus</i> (<i>Sundodrupeus</i>) <i>transversus</i>		+									
22.	<i>Mataeopsephus tenuipes</i>		+									
23.	<i>Afropsephenoides volatilis</i>		+									
24.	<i>Micreubrianax bellus</i>									+		
25.	<i>Psephenoides gahani</i>		+						+			
26.	<i>Psephenoides immsi</i>		+									
27.	<i>Psephenoides rajouri</i>		+									
28.	<i>Psephenoides subopacus</i>		+									

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